

ASAP Collaborative Research Network (CRN) Impact Report

2025-2026

An extension of the
2020-2024 CRN Impact Report

Table of Contents

Introduction	3
Collaboration	4
Facilitating Scientific Exchange Through Interest Groups	4
Solving Field-Wide Bottlenecks With Working Groups	5
Deepening Connections via Annual Meetings	5
Future Outlook	5
Resource Generation and Data Sharing	6
Generating Foundational Lab Materials	6
Building Integrated Data Platforms for Collaborative Discovery	7
Establishing Infrastructure and Standards for a Collaborative Ecosystem	9
Facilitating Transparent and Reusable Research Through Open Science Practices	10
Future Outlook	11
Accelerating Discovery	13
PD Functional Genomics	13
Neuro-Immune Interactions	16
Circuitry and Brain-Body Interactions in Parkinson's Disease	18
Future Outlook	21
Empowering the Next Generation	22
Interest Groups	22
Annual Meetings	22
Training & Development Infrastructure	22
Workshops	23
Future Outlook	23
Future of the ASAP Collaborative Research Network	24
Conclusion	24

Introduction

The **ASAP Collaborative Research Network (CRN)** is a global research community launched in 2020 to spark discoveries in Parkinson's disease (PD) research. The CRN leverages a collaborative network model and open science principles to generate field-enabling foundational resources and accelerate discoveries.

We evaluate our success through our three core principles:

Collaboration

Assessing our ability to facilitate connections and reshape the research ecosystem across our focus areas.

Resource Generation and Data Sharing

Evaluating our ability to develop new preclinical tools, resources, and datasets to transform PD research.

Accelerating Discoveries

Examining the network's findings and whether they have refined our understanding of the underlying mechanisms contributing to PD, which can be further funneled into the translational pipeline.

This report is an update of the **ASAP CRN Impact Report 2020-2024**, showcasing cross-cutting scientific themes across the CRN ecosystem, along with field-enabling resources, infrastructure efforts, and key discoveries.

Collaboration

Parkinson's disease (PD) is a multidimensional condition involving many complex biological systems spanning genetics, immunology, cellular biology, circuitry, and more. Addressing the multifaceted nature of PD requires experts from diverse fields to move beyond traditional research silos and work as an integrated system. ASAP views collaboration as a fundamental strategy for bridging gaps between research disciplines and accelerating the pace of scientific discovery in PD. Rather than dividing work into narrow fields, the Collaborative Research Network

(CRN) organizes its global community around broad research themes that serve as collaborative entry points, where investigators combine expertise and diverse perspectives to identify better and address knowledge gaps, ensuring the coordination of research priorities across the field.

Strategies to promote collaboration include:

- **Interest groups**
- **Working groups**
- **Annual meetings**

Facilitating Scientific Exchange Through Interest Groups

Interest Groups serve as a vital forum within the CRN for exchanging ideas, sharing preliminary findings, engaging trainees and young investigators, and fostering collaboration across teams working on related scientific questions. ASAP organizes these meetings to provide structured opportunities for discussing critical topics in PD. This model has proven to be a valuable mechanism for promoting innovation and inter-team collaboration. Topic-specific groups ensure targeted, high-value discussions take place to advance understanding of PD pathogenesis and progression. In 2025 and 2026, four interest group tracks in the CRN met over 100 times, covering major topics of scientific inquiry within PD:

- **The Pathology and Progression Interest Group** promotes discussion of the roles of synuclein and other pathogenic proteins, as well as downstream processes, in PD development and disease progression.
- **The PD Pathogenic Pathways Interest Group** promotes discussion around new and known

pathogenic pathways and mechanisms linked to PD, such as mitochondrial, endolysosomal, and immune pathways.

- **The Circuit Pathways Interest Group** promotes discussion around brain and non-brain circuits in PD pathogenesis and the development of PD symptoms.
- **The Cellular Subtyping Interest Group** promotes discussion of genetic and molecular phenotyping and the characterization of different cell types in the brain and other relevant regions linked to PD pathogenesis.

Interest groups are an important mechanism for identifying collaborations within the CRN. As indicated by a survey, nearly a third of those who presented at an interest group meeting have formed a new collaboration with someone from another ASAP team as a result. In one instance, a CRN team established three new collaborative projects through their involvement in interest groups.

Beyond formal collaborations, interest groups facilitate a coordinated effort to advance understanding of PD across CRN teams regardless

of expertise or research theme. The majority (65%) of interest group meetings in 2025 included presentations by teams from two or more research themes, catalyzing a shift toward integrative, multiscale frameworks. Key areas of progress include:

- **Multiscale Heterogeneity.** Resolving cellular and circuit diversity through subtype-specific functional mapping.
- **Organelle Convergence.** Linking genetic risk factors to lysosomal and mitochondrial dysfunction across cell types.
- **Physiological Modeling.** Advancing co-culture, organ-on-chip, and circuit-defined *in vivo* models.
- **Computational Synergy.** Utilizing machine learning to predict and quantify pathology across scales.

Solving Field-Wide Bottlenecks With Working Groups

Designed as focused, time-bound collaborations, working groups convene cross-team experts to produce practical, field-ready deliverables that strengthen rigor, reproducibility, and coordination across the PD research ecosystem. From 2021 to 2024, ASAP launched 15 investigator-driven working groups across the CRN to align protocols, harmonize datasets, and address shared scientific bottlenecks. Through 2025, 14 of these groups were successfully closed out, reflecting completion of defined goals and transition of outputs into sustained resources, including [iPSC](#)

[quality control recommendations](#), [behavioral assay guidelines](#), and [a standardized gut-PFF surgery protocol](#). (For more details, see the [ASAP CRN Impact Report 2020-2024](#).) Two working groups led to infrastructure advances: the launch of the [CRN Cloud data-sharing platform](#) and the establishment of a [Microbiome Analytics Core](#) to centralize analysis and standardize data from PD microbiome studies. Together, these outputs create shared standards, enable cross-network data integration, and contribute to greater consistency and transparency across the broader PD research field.

Deepening Connections via Annual Meetings

The CRN annual meetings serve as an important, in-person forum for sharing the latest findings, fostering collaboration, and addressing critical research gaps. These meetings bring together principal investigators, project managers, and, biannually, trainees from all CRN teams, along with external guests, to promote knowledge exchange and collaboration.

In 2025, 400 participants attended the CRN Collaborative Meeting. The majority (76.1%) of attendees stated that this meeting helped them identify a new collaboration, as indicated by a post-meeting survey. Additionally, nearly a third of participants appreciated the opportunities for spontaneous and informal conversations, noting that the meeting fosters a uniquely low-ego, high-impact collaborative environment.

Future Outlook

Looking ahead, there are exciting opportunities for collaboration within the PD research community, especially as our network expands to include the new [PD Heterogeneity](#) and [Tool Generation](#) CRN teams. The 2026 CRN Investigators Meeting, the 2026 Celebration for Scientific Achievement (COSA; for more information, see the [ASAP CRN Impact Report 2020-2024](#)), and the 2026 Discovery Fellows Summit will provide forums for sharing data, discussing emerging findings, and building cross-disciplinary partnerships. In addition, the development of new interest groups and working groups will create ongoing spaces for researchers to connect, exchange ideas, and pursue collaborative projects that advance the field.

Resource Generation and Data-Sharing

The ASAP initiative is founded on the principle that accelerating scientific discovery requires a steadfast commitment to collaboration, resource generation, and data sharing. Our core philosophy is that by supporting the development of critical research assets and ensuring these outputs are made widely available, we empower the entire scientific community to build upon existing work, validate new findings, and move more rapidly toward a cure. This approach is designed to dismantle research silos, create a more robust and collaborative research ecosystem for Parkinson's disease (PD), and facilitate a cumulative,

compounding effect on our collective knowledge. To achieve this, ASAP has implemented a strategic approach to identify and address the most critical needs within the PD research landscape.

After assessing the needs of the Collaborative Research Network (CRN) and the broader field, we have prioritized:

- **Generating foundational lab materials**
- **Building integrated data platforms**
- **Implementing progressive open science policies**

Generating Foundational Lab Materials

The development and dissemination of high-quality, validated biological reagents and disease models is the cornerstone of an efficient research ecosystem. These foundational resources are essential for ensuring experimental reproducibility, enabling the rigorous validation of emerging mechanisms, and providing the entire field with a common set of tools to interrogate the complex biology of PD.

ASAP PRECLINICAL TOOLS PROGRAM

The ASAP Preclinical Tools Program leverages The Michael J. Fox Foundation for Parkinson's Research (MJFF) Tools Program to support the development and deposition of novel, open-access laboratory reagents and models. By focusing on ASAP priority areas, the program ensures these tools are available for the research community to pursue and further interrogate emerging targets.

To date, the program has supported the development and/or distribution of over 140 resources, including:

- 93 standardized, gene-edited induced pluripotent stem cell (iPSC) lines completed (and 106 in development)
- 25 mutation-carrying embryonic stem cell lines with controls completed (and 19 in development)
- 11 knockout-validated antibody reagents completed (and 13 in development)
- 2 gene-edited immortalized cell lines completed (and 24 in development)
- 14 mouse models completed (and 2 in development)

Additionally, we have supported the dissemination of knowledge by adding:

- **35+ summaries of PD rodent model phenotypes to a preclinical model database**

Below are three examples of foundational lab materials we have supported based on resource gaps identified by our network:

1. INDI-PD iPSC Lines. Human iPSCs are critical for evaluating the biology of disease-related genetic mutations in relevant cell types from real patients. However, using donor cells with innumerable genetic differences makes it hard to determine the role of specific mutations in disease. Human iPSCs introduce disease-causing mutations to cell lines with the same genetic background, making it easier to study the direct relationship between a genetic mutation and its role in disease. ASAP supported the development and validation of 36 iPSC cell line sets (40 in development) for PD-associated gene knockouts. (Sets include heterozygous, homozygous, and revertant controls.) Together, these cell lines provide a quality-controlled toolbox of PD cell lines and genetically matched controls to improve reproducibility, provide novel insights into the molecular biology of PD, and enhance translational impact. [View the cell line catalog.](#)

2. Antibodies for endogenous organelle immunoprecipitation. The ability to isolate organelles to detect changes within subcellular compartments is useful for studying disease biology at the cellular level. However, commercially available antibodies are not ideal for immunoprecipitation (IP) of organelles. ASAP funded the generation and characterization of antibodies specifically designed for IP, including [human golgi \(anti-TMEM115\)](#), [human/mouse mitochondria \(anti-OMP25\)](#), and human lysosomes (anti-TMEM192; [unconjugated](#) and [bead-conjugated](#) formats).

3. LRRK2 KO Mouse Embryonic Fibroblasts (MEF) Lines. MEFs are valuable tools for studying protein biology related to PD. However, they are typically isolated from commercial mouse lines and, therefore, are not immortalized and cannot be easily shared with other researchers. Supporting the development of commercially available MEF

lines allows research to progress efficiently and circumvents the need to purchase mice and acquire animal care approvals to isolate MEFs.

These lines will be available at Abcam in 2026.

For additional details, search "ASAP" in the [MJFF Research Tools Catalog](#).

Building Integrated Data Platforms for Collaborative Discovery

ASAP's strategy recognizes that the value of data is multiplicative. To capitalize on the rich biological data being generated, we have strategically invested in building large-scale, harmonized repositories. This is not merely data storage. It is the deliberate construction of a computational ecosystem designed to break down legacy data silos and enable the complex, cross-disease analyses and next-generation algorithms required to unravel the deep complexities of neurodegenerative disease.

CRN CLOUD

Multi-omics data from postmortem human brain tissue and preclinical models are critical for studying neurodegenerative diseases like PD. However, storage and sharing of these often large datasets (>10 TB) remain challenging. Additionally, harmonization across datasets is uncommon, making it difficult to conduct analyses across multiple datasets.

The [CRN Cloud](#) platform provides a shared storage and analysis solution, bringing together and harmonizing omics data from multiple researchers within the ASAP CRN. The tool enables researchers to explore data at the individual-cell level and conduct analyses across datasets.

Currently, the CRN Cloud hosts >30 datasets, including data from hundreds of postmortem human brains, with more than 200 global users (including many not affiliated with ASAP), providing a harmonized foundation for complex meta-analyses. The scale of this resource is immense, encompassing 92.1 TB of data across 7,088 samples, including 674 single-cell or single-nucleus RNA-seq, 669 bulk RNA-seq, 600 spatial omics samples, and over 5,000 other omics samples.

By adhering to FAIR and open science principles, the CRN Cloud democratizes access to precious, limited postmortem brain tissue, ensuring that every sample yields the maximum possible scientific value. The infrastructure breaks down traditional academic silos, allowing international, multidisciplinary teams to share findings, protocols, and code in real-time. The harmonized CRN Cloud datasets provide a

standardized foundation that simplifies complex meta-analyses, which are essential for identifying rare disease biomarkers and genetic drivers. Ultimately, as the CRN Cloud continues to grow, it will house the largest dataset in brain transcriptomics and serve as a global engine for innovation, empowering the scientific community to move collectively closer to a cure. [View CRN Cloud data releases.](#)

CRN CLOUD DATA OVERVIEW – DETAILED

As of March 2026, with more data anticipated

Data Type	Subject and Sample Source (Counts)							
	Human				Mouse			
	Brain tissue (subj/samp)	Cell lines (subj/samp)	Gastro-intestinal (subj/samp)	Fecal (subj/samp)	Brain tissue (subj/samp)	Liver tissue (subj/samp)	Embryonic fibroblast (subj/samp)	Fecal (subj/samp)
sc/snRNA-seq	275 subj 598 samp	-	-	-	73 subj 76 samp			
Bulk RNA-seq	154 subj 613 samp	3 subj 32 samp	-	-	16 subj 16 samp	8 subj 8 samp		
Spatial Transcriptomics	126 subj 444 samp	-	33 subj 132 samp	-	6 subj 24 samp			48 subj 48 samp
Proteomics	-	1 subj 24 samp	-	-	-		66 subj 66 samp	
Genetics	94 subj 94 samp	-	-	-	-			
Metagenomics	-	-	-	464 subj 4,806 samp	-			

CRN CLOUD COLLABORATION WITH ALLEN INSTITUTE

Understanding the overlap between the clinical symptoms and pathobiology of neurodegenerative diseases like PD and Alzheimer's remains a challenge; and postmortem human brain samples are a rare and precious resource, critical for advancing our understanding of neurodegenerative diseases. Researchers can now access ASAP CRN Cloud data with the **Allen Brain Cell (ABC) Atlas**, a rich, interactive resource for exploring brain connectivity across diseases and species.

In 2025, the pilot integration was completed, with five CRN datasets released via the ABC Atlas alongside tutorials and joint marketing announcements. This collaboration establishes a shared language that aligns cell-type annotations to a standardized taxonomy and marks the first time data from patients with PD is included in the ABC Atlas, facilitating direct cross-disease comparisons between Parkinson's and Alzheimer's datasets. This interoperability improves data discoverability and will ultimately drive a deeper understanding of the cellular and molecular mechanisms of PD.

Establishing Infrastructure and Standards for a Collaborative Ecosystem

A truly collaborative ecosystem moves beyond data platforms alone and is built on a shared foundation of standards, infrastructure, and open science policies. Therefore, a key pillar of ASAP's 2025 strategy has been to invest in supporting open science practices, aligning on the common formats and protocols across teams, and providing expert support that enables researchers to share, compare, and reproduce their work seamlessly. These efforts are crucial for creating a research environment where the whole is greater than the sum of its parts.

CATALYST NEURO

Despite substantial progress in data sharing and open science, sharing neurophysiology data remains challenging due to the incompatibility of proprietary data formats with open-access repositories and the lack of in-house technical expertise in most labs. Through collaboration with **CatalystNeuro**, ASAP is directly lowering these barriers for ASAP teams by providing access to a centralized service for developing custom, lab-tailored pipelines that convert proprietary data into the standardized Neurodata Without Borders (NWB) format. CatalystNeuro also delivers training workshops and example notebooks to help labs use and modify these conversion tools independently, creating sustainable solutions that promote transparency and sharing of neurophysiology data.

Conversion pipelines and support have been provided to 13 ASAP-funded labs since the collaboration began in 2023. This collaboration has accelerated discovery through data reuse and created large, harmonized datasets essential for advancing artificial intelligence and machine learning applications. This work not only yields a publication multiplier effect but, most critically, drives a cultural transformation toward a more collaborative, open-science model for neurophysiology data.

MICROBIOME ANALYTICS CORE

Inconsistent metadata and a lack of harmonized processing have impeded rigorous cross-study comparisons of existing PD microbiome datasets. The Microbiome Analytics Core (MAC) supports data curation, metadata retrieval, standardized processing pipelines, data hosting, and analytical support for ASAP teams collecting microbiome-related datasets. MAC has compiled and standardized data from 70 published PD microbiome studies, creating the most comprehensive harmonized shotgun microbiome dataset in PD to date — approximately 40% larger than any previous comparable effort. 18 datasets have been fully processed using a consistent analytical pipeline and made publicly available, enabling researchers to easily access and analyze

high-quality, curated data. All resources, documentation, and progress tracking are openly shared to ensure transparency and broad usability. This **harmonized resource** now enables rigorous cross-study meta-analyses that were previously not possible. Early findings show consistent microbial patterns across studies, identify novel bacterial taxa potentially linked to PD, and support analyses examining the role of constipation, genetic variation (e.g., SNCA), and PD/control classification using machine learning approaches. Two manuscripts describing the curated resource and the meta-analysis are in development. Upon completion, MAC will provide the field with an openly accessible, standardized microbiome data platform that accelerates discovery and increases confidence in PD-related microbial findings.

Facilitating Transparent and Reusable Research Through Open Science Practices

In addition to supporting the generation of resources and related infrastructure, the CRN enforces a comprehensive and progressive open science policy that promotes the sharing of all research outputs (data, code & software, protocols, and key lab materials generated during a research study). Open science is essential for improving the speed, transparency, and reproducibility of research, while maximizing the impact of scientific discoveries across the research community.

PREPRINTS

By requiring CRN grantees to post their research findings as preprints, we have enabled faster sharing of discoveries in PD. Since 2024, over 95% of manuscripts reporting original research by CRN grantees have been posted as preprints, compared with **the fieldwide average of ~15%**. Working with OpenRxiv, ASAP has established a **bioRxiv/medRxiv Channel** where anyone can read ASAP-funded preprints, the vast majority of which include an open license allowing for unrestricted reuse. As of April

2026, the channel housed 500 preprints, which were posted a median of 9 months before publication in a journal and collectively, have received more than 1.1 million views, 250,000 downloads, and 1,600 citations. When shared as preprints, CRN research findings inform ongoing research efforts at a pace unattainable with traditional publishing.

KEY RESOURCE TABLES

Each CRN publication now comes with a Key Resource Table. These tables itemize where another researcher can access each dataset, analysis script, software, experimental protocol, and key lab material used and generated in a CRN study. These tables make the building blocks of scientific discovery visible, allowing researchers to more easily build on the work of others, collaborate, and verify existing findings. Use of the Key Resource Tables also allows tracking of the tools and resources being used and generated in the CRN. Over the last year of CRN research, more than 10,000 resources have gone into and come out of the CRN research ecosystem.

TRANSPARENT RESEARCH STANDARDS

We mandate the sharing of detailed protocols and adherence to metadata standards to improve the reproducibility, consistency, and interoperability of research outputs across labs and institutions. For example, we require that protocols be shared via **protocols.io**. To date, CRN grantees have shared 2,921 protocols on protocols.io, of which 1,934 are public. This approach ensures transparency in how science is done, allowing other researchers to understand, reproduce, and build upon every step of an experiment. Additionally, we share guidance and metadata standards for **datasets, code, quality control experiments**, and more. These metadata standards capture essential information about experimental design, instrumentation, preprocessing steps, and validation procedures, making datasets and code understandable and reusable by others. Overall, these policies strengthen scientific rigor, facilitate transparency, and accelerate progress across the broader research community.

Future Outlook

Scientific progress requires advancing from initial discovery to replication and validation; however, the infrastructure required to support this step is often underdeveloped or absent. Anticipating this gap, we are focusing on building the necessary infrastructure in advance so that, as new findings emerge from ASAP-funded projects, the field is equipped to validate and reproduce them rigorously. Additionally, we are focused on addressing large-scale, standing questions in the field that slow progress towards understanding the mechanisms of PD and developing effective, disease-modifying therapies. Below are examples of projects we are supporting to build capacity and advance the PD field:

Neuropathology Resources

The research community lacks access to large-scale, cross-disease, curated neuropathology image datasets. This scarcity has limited the development of gold-standard quantification algorithms and made cross-disease analyses difficult. In 2025, ASAP partnered with **The 10,000 Brains Project** and MJFF to build a community-friendly, AI-ready repository for a global cohort of digitized pathology data. 10,000 Brains will lead data curation, development, and maintenance of a Verily Workbench-based research gateway.

In parallel, ASAP created a centralized, searchable resource to collate **brain tissue inventory** information across contributing brain banks. Together, these efforts are expected to improve visibility, access, and reuse of existing biospecimens by the broader research community and enable the development of gold-standard quantification and analysis algorithms and power novel investigations, including an initial planned analysis of sex differences in PD pathology across 1,500 cases.

Immune Consortium

As we move beyond a "one-size-fits-all" approach to PD, understanding the role of the immune system is critical. However, immune research in PD cohorts

remains fragmented, with inconsistent sample collection and a lack of assay standardization, which limits the development of immune biomarkers and therapeutic strategies. The Immune Consortium, an ASAP supported program in partnership with MJFF, was launched in 2025 to systematically evaluate existing resources, define best practices, validate assays, and drive data-driven immune discovery.

The Immune Consortium supports four coordinated workstreams:

- Multi-cohort resourcing to strategically run additional immune assays in well-defined cohorts with existing peripheral blood mononuclear cell (PBMC) collections
- PBMC collection protocol alignment to understand the existing limitations for this invaluable resource
- Functional assay alignment to test robustness for key functional assays testing immune function
- Hypothesis generation through the mining of existing datasets

As of late 2025, landscape analyses of existing resources are nearly complete, protocol comparison experiments are underway, and analytical plans are defined for execution in 2026. In early 2026, a new funding opportunity was announced to identify specific immune cell populations and functional states that correlate with PD disease risk, onset, and progression. For more information, see the **[MJFF Immune Profiling Insights Program page](#)**. This foundational work will create a standardized and scalable immune research infrastructure, which has the potential to reshape the understanding of immunity's role in PD by enabling high-quality biomarker discovery and facilitating future longitudinal immune studies.

Guided Photometry Analysis in Python

Fiber photometry is a powerful technique for measuring population-level neural activity in freely behaving animals, making it particularly valuable for understanding circuit dysfunction in movement

disorders like PD. While the experimental hardware for fiber photometry is increasingly standardized, analysis of fiber photometry data relies heavily on lab-specific custom code, creating significant barriers for data sharing and cross-laboratory collaboration. In 2025, ASAP began supporting the enhancement of Guided Photometry Analysis in Python (GuPPy), a standardized, open-source software platform for fiber photometry analysis, to ensure its long-term sustainability.

Long-term upgrades and maintenance of GuPPy will provide a standardized analysis pipeline for fiber photometry datasets that can be used across laboratories in the PD field. Additionally, these upgrades will enable integration with the Neurodata Without Borders (NWB) data standard and DANDI Archive, facilitating large-scale, cross-lab meta-analysis and standardization of photometry analysis across the field.

Open Science 2.0

The CRN launched with an ambitious Open Science Policy to ensure all CRN research outputs were openly shared with the research community. **We have largely met this goal.** Recently, we expanded our open science efforts to champion **Open Science 2.0**, an ecosystem where researchers seamlessly interact to build on one another's work, and where research infrastructure and cultural norms have evolved to foster efficient and widespread collaboration in real time. **Our updated Open Science Policy** requires that CRN researchers deposit all research outputs by the time of posting a preprint. Furthermore, the updated policy requires raw data to be shared in a community-recognized, datatype-specific repository, with metadata structured to support seamless reuse and integration with other datasets. These requirements shift the focus from simple data preservation to active, real-time scientific exchange.

New Round of Funding: CRN 2026

To continue building on this work, we are supporting new research infrastructure projects, especially those focused on validating and reproducing findings from previous CRN teams. New projects funded in 2026 include **6 teams focusing on tool development** and **10 meta-analysis projects** utilizing existing CRN-generated omics data.

The **Tool Generation** theme is focused on supporting the development of novel, sustainable, and field-enabling tools for emerging targets identified through previous ASAP-funded research. These projects will create, validate, and globally distribute high-quality resources in collaboration with commercial repositories or academic cores. Projects include development of novel model systems (e.g., iPSC and mouse models), chemical probes and viral vectors to modulate activity or expression levels, and antibodies and assays to detect and measure targets. By developing accessible, reliably produced tools for the PD community, this theme aims to remove bottlenecks in PD research and accelerate therapeutic development for targets identified through ASAP research.

Training & Development

Multi-omics Meta-analysis

The **Multi-omics Meta-analysis (MoMa)** program funds existing

CRN researchers to conduct meta-analyses of omics data stored in the CRN Cloud by two or more CRN teams. By promoting analysis across multiple large datasets collected using diverse assays and techniques, these projects aim to facilitate replication and identify common patterns and novel mechanistic insights, which are only possible with the scale and depth of data available in the CRN Cloud.

Accelerating Discoveries

The ASAP Collaborative Research Network (CRN) comprises 35 teams focused on understanding the mechanisms underlying the pathogenesis and progression of Parkinson's disease (PD). The CRN is strategically organized around broad, collaborative themes designed to break down research silos and

accelerate discovery. This summary highlights significant progress within three of these core themes:

- **PD Functional Genomics**
- **Neuro-Immune Interactions**
- **Circuitry and Brain-Body Interactions**

PD Functional Genomics

The PD Functional Genomics theme is dedicated to both understanding and identifying genetic risk factors for PD as well as unraveling their precise biological consequences. The primary goal is to understand the molecular and cellular pathways these genes disrupt, a critical step toward developing therapies that target the root causes of idiopathic and sporadic PD. In 2025, significant strides were made in connecting disparate genetic mutations to shared biological processes and in developing powerful new tools to measure the disease's impact on the brain.

See research outputs shared to date.

SCIENTIFIC HIGHLIGHTS

Across the network, 14 CRN teams collectively contributed to advancing our understanding of PD in which mitochondrial dysfunction, lysosomal impairment, innate immune activation, RNA-processing defects, and altered cellular energetics interact and converge across vulnerable neuronal and glial populations. Their findings reveal that early pathogenic events occur well before Lewy pathology, often in brain regions previously thought unaffected. Together, this integrated body of work provides a mechanistic framework for targeting PD at multiple upstream nodes before irreversible neurodegeneration occurs.

Convergent Mechanisms of Organelle Stress: Mitochondria, Lysosomes, Lipids, and Polyamines

Years of untangling the biological basis of PD have revealed that diverse genetic mutations associated with PD risk are not isolated actors, but likely converge on a common set of cellular pathways. Often, these pathways are critical for normal cellular homeostasis, such as endolysosomal, mitochondrial, and inflammatory pathways. In disease, disruptions to the normal sequence of these biological pathways lead to dysfunction of these important cellular processes. A unified model emerging from CRN research shows that mitochondrial dysfunction, lysosomal stress, lipid imbalance, and polyamine dysregulation form an interconnected network of vulnerabilities that drive PD pathogenesis across genotypes, showcasing that these cellular pathways may represent universal failure points in both idiopathic and sporadic PD.

Selected Publications:

- **Reconstitution of BNIP3/NIX-mitophagy initiation reveals hierarchical flexibility of the autophagy machinery** | Team Hurley has expanded our understanding of mitochondrial quality control mechanisms by discovering new ways to initiate mitophagy.
- **MAPL regulates gasdermin-mediated release of mtDNA from lysosomes to drive pyroptotic**

cell death | Team Desjardins has found that MAPL induces pyroptosis through an inflammatory pathway involving mitochondria and lysosomes, and that multiple PD-related genes also regulate MAPL-induced pyroptosis.

- **Loss of the lysosomal lipid flippase ATP10B leads to progressive dopaminergic neurodegeneration** | Team Vangheluwe has identified lysosomal polyamine-lipid cross-talk as a driver of dysregulated lysosomal transport and dopaminergic neuron degeneration.
- **A STING-CASM-GABARAP pathway activates LRRK2 at lysosomes** | Team De Camilli defined a pathway that integrates multiple stimuli at lysosomes to regulate LRRK2 kinase activity.
- **Lysosomal glucocerebrosidase is needed for ciliary Hedgehog signaling: A convergent pathway contributing to Parkinson's disease and Endogenous LRRK2 and PINK1 function in a convergent neuroprotective ciliogenesis pathway in the brain** | Team Alessi showed that GBA1, PINK1, and LRRK2 converge on cilia-dependent Hedgehog signaling and that restoring ciliary function with LRRK2 inhibitors rescues defects.
- **GPNMB is a biomarker of lysosomal dysfunction and is secreted via LRRK2-modulated lysosomal exocytosis** | Team Hardy found that GPNMB is secreted in response to lysosomal stress and that LRRK2 is a strong modulator of GPNMB secretion.

By identifying these convergent pathways and their interactions with genetic risk factors, this research identifies shared biological failure points that could be targeted therapeutically. It provides novel insights into disease risk and pathobiology. Understanding these pathways warrants continued mechanistic exploration and future translational efforts to evaluate how interventions may address the broader pathophysiology of PD. Such findings also underscore the need for continued efforts to explore interactions with other genetic risk factors for PD, and for other neurodegenerative disease states.

Genetic Architecture & RNA Biology: From Multi-Omics to Mechanisms

Previous and ongoing genetic studies have revealed that genetic risk factors are not limited to highly penetrant coding mutations. Researchers across the CRN have been investigating how non-coding variation mediates genetic risk, the mechanisms that underlie its effects, and how it leads to downstream changes in relevant biological pathways. By integrating genomics with other profiling technologies, CRN teams are building more sophisticated models that may provide new insights relevant to therapeutic intervention. Such efforts build on important findings in statistical, genetic, and functional genomics, bringing them closer to the translational pipeline.

Selected Publications:

- **Circular RNAs in the human brain are tailored to neuron identity and neuropsychiatric disease** | Team Scherzer investigated the significance of circular RNA transcripts in disease, showing that some circular RNAs correlate with various neurological conditions. These represent starting points for future evaluations of understudied forms of transcriptional regulation.
- **Splicing accuracy varies across human introns, tissues, and age** | Teams Hardy and Wood identified alterations in the structure of RNAs across postmortem brain tissues, with notable changes throughout life.
- **Activation of transposable elements is linked to a region- and cell-type-specific interferon response in Parkinson's disease** | Team Jakobsson revealed that certain transposable genetic elements (TEs) are activated in PD, suggesting a potential role in pathology, and highlighting an understudied form of genetic risk.

Through these and other efforts, CRN researchers have expanded our understanding of underexplored forms of genetic risk and how these translate fundamental biology into pathological mechanisms. Such findings have the potential to identify novel

targets for preventive or disease-modifying therapeutics. They may also inform our understanding of tissue- and cell-type-specific differences in susceptibility to PD initiation and progression. As novel technologies emerge, work in this space provides better clarity on the directionality of effect and the regulatory processes that mediate disease.

Early Immune Activation & Proteinopathy as Upstream Drivers

Prevalent hypotheses in the PD field implicate the immune system and protein aggregation in the pathogenesis and progression of PD. While much work remains to disentangle the importance and contributions of these triggers fully, research across the CRN has collectively increased our understanding of this question. A unifying model has emerged showing that early immune activation, triggered by α -synuclein oligomers, lysosomal stress, mitochondrial danger signals, and innate immune pathways, precedes Lewy pathology and drives disease progression.

Selected Publications:

- **ER-lysosome lipid transfer protein VPS13C/ PARK23 prevents aberrant mtDNA-dependent STING signaling** | Team De Camilli showed that loss of VPS13C triggers accumulation of lysosomes and activates the cGAS-STING innate immune pathway.
- **Activation of transposable elements is linked to a region- and cell-type-specific interferon response in Parkinson's disease** | Team Jakobsson found that activation of transposable elements altered the expression of interferon-related and viral response genes, indicating that this activation can contribute to neuroinflammatory processes that affect PD progression.
- **α -Synuclein aggregates inhibit ESCRT-III through sequestration and collateral degradation** | Team Harper identified a mechanism wherein depletion of ESCRT-III by interaction with α -synuclein fibrils amplifies lysosomal rupture and inflammation.

- **ATP13A2-mediated endo-lysosomal polyamine export counters mitochondrial oxidative stress** | Team Vangheluwe found that ATP13A2-mediated polyamine imbalance triggers astrocytic inflammation and dopaminergic neuron degeneration.

By understanding the contributions of the immune system and protein aggregation to PD pathogenesis and progression, we will make strides in biomarker discovery and targeted therapeutic approaches. Given the close links between inflammation and cellular mechanisms, further work in these fields will continue to help untangle the complex molecular and cellular network that contributes to PD.

Modulating LRRK2 Kinase Activity as a Central Therapeutic Strategy

Increased LRRK2 kinase activity is observed in both genetic and idiopathic PD cases, suggesting aberrant LRRK2 hyperactivity is a central node in PD pathogenesis. This discovery has focused therapeutic development on modulating LRRK2 activity. CRN researchers have identified modulators of LRRK2 kinase activity, opening new avenues for novel therapeutic strategies to dampen the effects of hyperactive LRRK2.

Selected Publications:

- **PPM1M, a LRRK2-counteracting, phosphoRab12-preferring phosphatase with potential link to Parkinson's disease** | Team Alessi has identified PPM1M as a key player in the LRRK2 signaling pathway, which may represent a novel therapeutic target.
- **Allosteric regulation of the Golgi-localized PPM1H phosphatase by Rab GTPases modulates LRRK2 substrate dephosphorylation in Parkinson's disease** | Team Alessi showed that PPM1H has binding sites for Rab8A and Rab10, which could be therapeutically relevant sites to enhance PPM1H-mediated dephosphorylation of LRRK2 substrates for those with LRRK2-driven PD.

- **Type-II kinase inhibitors that target Parkinson's Disease-associated LRRK2** | Team Reck-Peterson identified structural states of LRRK2 and developed Type-2 inhibitors capable of preventing microtubule binding and lysosomal activation.

Together, this body of work has uncovered novel targets for counteracting LRRK2-driven pathology in PD. Findings in this field have led to the pursuit of novel LRRK2-targeting approaches through the MJFF-led **LRRK2 Investigative Therapeutics Exchange (LITE) program**.

Neuro-Immune Interactions

The Neuro-Immune Interactions theme investigates the immune system's specific roles in PD. For years, neuroinflammation has been recognized as a feature of the PD brain, but the precise molecular and cellular contributors remained unknown. The goal of this theme is to move beyond this general observation to identify the specific immune pathways and cell types that drive disease, thereby opening the door to novel therapeutic strategies targeting the immune system. **See research outputs shared to date.**

SCIENTIFIC HIGHLIGHTS

Across the network, 7 CRN teams collectively contributed to expanding our understanding of the specific immune pathways involved in PD pathogenesis and their interactions with known PD-risk genes, including T cell autoreactivity, immune dysregulation in the gut, and astrocytic RNA editing. Their findings reveal that genes and inflammation converge to amplify PD risk and progression. Together, this integrated body of work lays the groundwork for novel, immune-targeted therapeutic strategies and biomarkers.

Linking Genetic Mutations to Gut and Immune Dysregulation

Emerging evidence suggests that genetic risk factors for PD may shape how the gut and immune system respond to inflammation, infection, and microbial imbalance. Across the CRN, teams have investigated how mutations in genes such as LRRK2 and PINK1 influence immune cell function, intestinal inflammation, and systemic immune signaling. These studies reveal that PD-associated mutations can amplify gut inflammation, alter neutrophil and other innate immune responses, and produce measurable changes in immune markers in blood and cerebrospinal fluid. Complementary mechanistic work further explores how gut inflammation may contribute to α -synuclein propagation and Lewy body pathology.

Selected Publications:

- **LRRK2 G2019S mutation incites increased cell-intrinsic neutrophil effector functions and intestinal inflammation** and **PINK1 deficiency rewires early immune responses in a mouse model of Parkinson's disease triggered by intestinal infection** | Team Desjardins found that LRRK2 and PINK1 are key regulators of immune functions in the gut during infection, highlighting a link between immune cell dysregulation and PD pathogenesis.
- **Lewy body diseases and the gut** | Team Liddle wrote a review article detailing the hypotheses and existing research about the gut-brain α -synuclein propagation model.
- **Soluble immune factor profiles in blood and CSF associated with LRRK2 mutations and Parkinson's disease** | Team Chen found several serum markers that were altered in LRRK2 mutation carriers and PD, suggesting these serum markers could be utilized for PD biomarker efforts.

Together, this work strengthens the link between genetic risk, immune dysregulation, and gut-brain mechanisms in PD. Further research is needed to continue unraveling the complex interactions between genetic risk and inflammation to advance potential biomarker and therapeutic strategies.

Spotlight on α -Synuclein Pathology in the Gut: Where does PD Begin?

The hypothesis that Parkinson's disease (PD) originates in the gastrointestinal (GI) tract and propagates to the brain (the "gut-first" model) via α -synuclein transmission has strongly influenced investment in PD research. The prevalence of early GI symptoms supports this framework, observed enteric pathology in established PD, epidemiologic studies of vagotomy, and robust gut-inoculation models in rodents. However, this framework requires that pathological α -synuclein be present in the gut before the brain in humans. To date, this assumption has remained largely unvalidated, as no neuropathology lab has yet found a single case of GI synucleinopathy in the absence of brain synucleinopathy.

With many CRN teams investigating the "gut-first" model of Parkinson's, ASAP strategically funded The GI Project as a targeted, focused project in addition to the CRN Team awards. The GI Project was a collaboration between the **Caughey-Orru** and **Beach-Serrano** labs to test the gut-first premise using high-resolution human autopsy data directly. The study combined extensive sampling across 10 GI tract regions with highly sensitive seeded amplification assays (SAA) in 179 neuropathologically characterized subjects, including neurologically normal controls, incidental Lewy body disease (iLBD; a putative preclinical state), and clinically diagnosed PD.

The findings were consistent and decisive. GI α -synuclein pathology was nearly universal and widespread in PD and tightly correlated with the extent of brain pathology. In iLBD, GI involvement scaled with brain α -synuclein burden and followed a rostral-caudal gradient. Critically, isolated GI synucleinopathy was exceedingly rare, occurring convincingly in only a single case, while brain-only pathology was at least 16.5-fold more common. These data indicate that α -synuclein pathology most often begins in the brain, with GI involvement emerging secondary to or, in some cases, in parallel with early brain stages.

This suggests that continued reliance on gut-based pre-formed fibril animal models as default representations of PD carries translational risk. These models lack sufficient validity to serve as a dominant or generalizable framework for human PD. While gut-to-brain propagation is a powerful experimental paradigm, it likely represents a minority disease trajectory. The gut remains biologically relevant in PD, but its role is more plausibly mediated through non-propagative pathways, such as intestinal barrier dysfunction, microbiome-driven immune activation, and systemic inflammation, rather than direct α -synuclein transmission to the brain. **[Read the preprint.](#)**

Defining Immune Cell Reactivity in PD

Growing evidence suggests that immune dysfunction, particularly T-cell autoreactivity, may be an early and fundamental feature of PD pathogenesis. Across the CRN, teams have examined how adaptive and innate immune responses interact with α -synuclein pathology during prodromal and established stages of disease. These studies reveal elevated T cell reactivity to α -synuclein and PINK1, sex-specific immune differences, and pro-inflammatory myeloid signaling processes that may drive early neurodegeneration. Complementary work highlights

the dual role of astrocytes: initially protecting the brain by clearing α -synuclein aggregates, but transitioning to a sustained inflammatory state as pathology progresses.

Selected Publications:

- **[Inflamed microglia, like macrophages in the central nervous system of prodromal Parkinson's disease](#)** | Team Hafler investigated the role of inflammation in the pathogenesis of prodromal PD. They uncovered a myeloid-mediated TNF α inflammatory process, suggesting a novel pathological mechanism.

- **T cell responses towards PINK1 and α -synuclein are elevated in prodromal Parkinson's disease and Differential memory enrichment of cytotoxic CD4 T cells in Parkinson's disease patients reactive to α -synuclein** | Team Sulzer explored variables that contribute to T cell responses to α -synuclein, including sex and the presence of CD4 memory cells. They found that males with PD had elevated T cell reactivity compared with healthy controls and females with PD, underscoring the need to further explore sex-specific biological differences in neuroinflammation and PD.
- **Astrocytic RNA editing regulates the host immune response to α -synuclein** | Team Wood found an astrocyte-specific neuroinflammatory response in PD, wherein dysregulation of an RNA editing enzyme, in combination with α -synuclein aggregation, may lead to sustained inflammatory reactive states.
- **Transgenic A53T mice have astrocytic α -synuclein aggregates in dopamine and striatal regions** | Team Kirik investigated the role of astrocytes in PD and found that astrocytes normally clear α -synuclein and that the substantia nigra pars compacta requires more astrocytic support than other midbrain dopaminergic regions.

Together, these findings deepen our understanding of how peripheral and central immune mechanisms contribute to PD onset and progression, informing new avenues for biomarker development and immune-targeted therapies.

Circuitry & Brain-Body Interactions

The Circuitry & Brain-Body

Interactions theme aims to understand PD not merely as a disease of isolated dopamine-producing neurons, but as a system-level disorder that affects entire neural circuits and the intricate communication

between the brain and peripheral systems, such as the gut. The goal is to map how disruptions across interconnected networks contribute to symptoms and disease progression, thereby identifying new points for therapeutic intervention. **See research outputs shared to date.**

SCIENTIFIC HIGHLIGHTS

Across the network, 14 CRN teams collectively advanced our understanding of a systemic view of PD, in which neuromodulatory signaling, synaptic input, activity patterns, bioenergetic stress, and age-related factors converge on dopaminergic neurons to drive vulnerability to neurodegeneration. Their findings reveal a complex interplay of intrinsic and extrinsic factors, both in the brain and the periphery, that drive pathogenesis in PD. Together, this integrated body of work identifies specific cellular failure points that drive vulnerability in PD patients and could be modulated for therapeutic impact.

Expanded Understanding of Dopamine-Acetylcholine Interactions

Acetylcholine released from striatal cholinergic interneurons interacts closely with dopamine to regulate striatal motor output. In health, the dopaminergic-cholinergic balance is finely tuned; however, following dopamine signaling loss in PD, this balance is disrupted. How acetylcholine and dopamine dynamically interact during normal behavior and how this interplay is altered in disease remain open questions. A growing body of work from the CRN is dissecting the circuit-level mechanisms through which these systems coordinate motor control and contribute to PD.

Selected Publications:

- **An axonal brake on striatal dopamine output by cholinergic interneurons** | Team Cragg found that cholinergic interneurons transiently suppress dopamine release in the striatum by impairing the translation of action potentials into dopamine release.

- **Distinct spatially organized striatum-wide acetylcholine dynamics for the learning and extinction of Pavlovian associations** | Team Cragg identified regional and temporal differences in acetylcholine and dopamine signaling during behavior, suggesting timing, brain region, and context play important roles in the interaction between neuromodulators.
- **Postsynaptic adaptations in direct pathway muscarinic M4-receptor signaling follow the temporal and regional pattern of dopaminergic degeneration** | Team Edwards demonstrated temporal and regional changes to cholinergic modulation following dopaminergic depletion.

Acetylcholine represents a promising, non-dopaminergic therapeutic target for PD. By deepening our understanding of dopamine-acetylcholine interactions in health and disease, this work expands our knowledge of a critically important circuit in movement and learning that is disrupted in PD and moves the field closer to new therapeutic modalities.

Identifying Properties of Vulnerable Neurons

A central challenge in PD research is understanding the selective vulnerability of dopaminergic neurons. Although their preferential degeneration is thought to arise from intrinsic properties, the pathophysiological mechanisms that precede and drive cell death remain unclear. Several studies have identified molecular subtypes of vulnerable dopaminergic neurons, such as Anxa1-expressing populations, but moving beyond molecular markers is essential to understand how intrinsic and extrinsic factors interact to promote neurodegeneration. Recent research in the CRN has identified several contributors to this selective vulnerability in PD, including distinctive activity patterns, bioenergetic stress, microcircuit interactions, dysregulated iron handling, and age-related neuromelanin accumulation.

Selected Publications:

- **Chronic hyperactivation of midbrain dopamine neurons causes preferential dopamine neuron degeneration** | Team Edwards found that chronic chemogenetic excitation of dopaminergic neurons is sufficient to induce degeneration of SNc, but not VTA, dopaminergic neurons.
- **Neuromodulatory control of energy reserves in dopaminergic neurons** | Team De Camilli demonstrated a bidirectional relationship between glycogen stores and neuronal activity in dopaminergic neurons. When dopaminergic input is lost (as in PD), the cells become more sensitive to bioenergetic stress.
- **Parkinson's disease-vulnerable and -resilient dopamine neurons display opposite responses to excitatory input** | Team Awatramani found that vulnerable and resilient neurons in PD responded differently to the same excitatory inputs, suggesting that the microcircuit(s) to which a cell belongs may shape its susceptibility to degeneration.
- **Sex-dimorphic effects of neuromelanin buildup in rodent nigral dopamine neurons: implications for sex-based vulnerability in Parkinson's disease** | Team Vila demonstrated a role of neuromelanin accumulation, which occurs with age, in preferential vulnerability of dopaminergic neurons and the development of non-motor symptoms of PD.
- **Iron mishandling in the brain and periphery in Parkinson's disease** | Team Liddle proposes that alterations to iron handling in the SNc dopaminergic neurons may contribute to neurodegeneration.

This body of work provides a multi-faceted, mechanistic framework for understanding the selective vulnerability of dopaminergic neurons in PD, moving beyond molecular markers alone, to reveal how intrinsic cellular properties intersect with

external stressors and age-related factors to drive degeneration, underscoring the importance of cellular context. This paves the way for new therapeutic targets and precision medicine by identifying specific cellular failure points driving vulnerability in PD patients.

Peripheral and Systemic Contributions to Disease

Exposure to environmental toxicants, such as pesticides and viral infections, is a known risk factor for PD. Cells in the periphery, specifically the gut and olfactory bulb, sit at the interface of the environment and the brain, suggesting that peripheral and systemic insults may impact the onset and progression of PD. However, the evidence supporting a body-first hypothesis for PD is limited. Integrated CRN findings indicate that PD risk is modulated through peripheral pathways, in which gastrointestinal inflammation, toxicant exposure, and the microbiome contribute to α -synuclein pathology.

Selected Publications:

- **The gut microbiome promotes mitochondrial respiration in the brain of a Parkinson's disease mouse model** | Team Gradinaru found that dysregulation of mitochondrial function (increased mitochondrial respiration and oxidative stress) is induced by the microbiome.
- **Metagenomics of Parkinson's disease implicates the gut microbiome in multiple disease mechanisms** | Team Liddle showed widespread dysbiosis in the PD metagenome, indicative of an environment permissive to neurodegeneration and disease.
- **The pyrethroid insecticide deltamethrin disrupts neuropeptide and monoamine signaling pathways in the gastrointestinal tract** | Team Liddle demonstrated that exposure to an environmental toxicant induces constipation and impairs intestinal hormone signaling, symptoms often seen in PD patients.
- **Gut mucosal cells transfer alpha-synuclein to the vagus nerve** | Team Liddle found that α -synuclein can spread cell-to-cell, from gut cells to vagal neurons in the nodose ganglia.
- **Elevated brain alpha-synuclein, phosphorylated-tau, and oxidative stress in mice that survived influenza A pneumonitis** | Team Schlossmacher demonstrated that a peripheral viral infection led to sustained, chronic alterations in levels of several neurodegeneration markers, which were exacerbated by PD risk variants.
- **Development of a simplified smell test to identify Parkinson's disease using multiple cohorts, machine learning, and item response theory** | Team Schlossmacher described olfactory dysfunction (hyposmia) in PD and a test that can distinguish PD subtypes from healthy controls.

This work supports the role of peripheral and systemic insults in the onset and progression of PD, and helps to clarify the long-standing question of the role of the gut in PD pathogenesis. Because these symptoms often appear prior to motor deficits, detection of alterations in the gut microbiome or hyposmia is a key biomarker for early detection and diagnosis of PD that can occur in a family medicine office.

Future Outlook

The initial rounds of ASAP funding meaningfully advanced the field, generating new insights and momentum that have opened up an important next set of scientific questions. Building on this progress, we have funded **26 new team projects** to push the boundaries of discovery in PD research.

New Round of Funding: CRN 2026

The **PD Heterogeneity** theme focuses on supporting high-priority projects to explore the mechanisms underlying the different manifestations of PD and to unpack variability in disease onset, symptoms, and progression rates. Projects focus on the roles of aging, co-pathologies, environmental risk factors, cellular clearance mechanisms, and α -synuclein seeding in disease, as well as on the neural circuitry underlying debilitating non-motor symptoms experienced by PD patients, such as sleep disturbances, cognitive dysfunction, and chronic pain. Additionally, all projects funded in this theme focus on integrating preclinical findings with human data, helping ensure that the deep mechanistic insights emerging from ASAP-funded preclinical work have the highest translational potential. By understanding these diverse drivers, this theme aims to propel the field beyond "one-size-fits-all" treatments toward precision medicine tailored to specific patient subtypes.

Empowering the Next Generation

ASAP believes that the future of Parkinson’s disease (PD) research begins with empowering a strong, diverse, and global research community. ASAP is building the next generation of PD researchers by fostering opportunities for collaboration and active scientific engagement, providing training courses, workshops, and resources to support professional development, and supporting innovative and creative science. These experiences help trainees build professional connections, identify possible

collaborations, receive constructive feedback, and develop the skills needed to thrive in the research community.

Trainees participate in the Collaborative Research Network (CRN) through:

- **Interest groups**
- **Annual meetings**
- **Training & development opportunities**
- **Workshops**

Interest Groups

Trainees are highly encouraged to present their findings at interest group meetings. In 2025, 80% of interest group presentations were by trainees or young investigators, providing trainees with the opportunity to present their work and receive feedback from leaders in the PD field, and increasing trainee visibility within the CRN. These opportunities positively affect trainees' experience, with over 95% of trainees who have presented at interest groups finding the experience valuable to their training, as indicated by a survey.

“These groups have been a great platform for learning how to structure and deliver professional presentations. The feedback I’ve received has not only improved my scientific progress but also helped me refine how I communicate my findings to a diverse audience.” – CRN Trainee

Annual Meetings

Trainees were invited to participate in the 2025 CRN Collaborative Meeting. 124 trainees from 34 teams attended. During this meeting, trainees presented their research findings through dedicated poster sessions and selected main-session talks. Trainees were also able to participate in **hands-on workshops** about open science data practices and utilizing the CRN Cloud platform. In addition, trainees participated in career chats with professionals across multiple scientific disciplines to learn about career paths.

Training & Development Infrastructure

Training & Development

In 2025, ASAP launched a Training &

Development resource team, which serves as a centralized hub for ASAP CRN trainees and emerging professionals, offering opportunities for skill-building

and career exploration, fostering connections within the research community, and promoting fellowships, funding, and job opportunities. This team provides the infrastructure and framework for all trainee-related opportunities, including career and skills workshops, the biennial Celebration for Scientific Achievement (COSA; for more information, see the [ASAP CRN Impact Report 2020-2024](#)), the [Care & Career Program](#), and more. The goal of Team Training & Development is to provide support and resources to the next generation of Parkinson's disease researchers.

Workshops

Trainees have opportunities to expand their technical skills and open science mindset through workshops provided by ASAP. At the 2025 CRN Collaborative Meeting, two in-person workshops were hosted for trainees to learn more about open science and data sharing. The [CRN Cloud](#) hosted a workshop that covered the CRN Cloud ecosystem, data types, and organization, finding and connection data collections to Verily Workbench for analysis (including a hands-on demonstration!), and tips for data sharing, storage, and cost management. The Open Science Team also hosted a workshop focused on best practices for data sharing, curation, and documentation, with a hands-on exploration of real data from the CRN.

Future Outlook

Postdoctoral fellows are the future leaders of PD research and essential drivers of innovation. To infuse fresh ideas into the field and foster the next generation of leadership in PD research, we have funded 23 projects from postdoctoral fellows on CRN teams.

New Round of Funding: CRN 2026

**Training &
Development**

Discovery Fellowship

The **Discovery Fellowship** is a competitive award designed to elevate exceptional postdoctoral research fellows towards independent research careers. These fellowships support bold, trainee-led projects that leverage inter-team collaboration and foster mentor-mentee relationships. Projects utilize a unique

joint mentorship structure, in which Fellows propose a novel research project that combines the resources and expertise of their own CRN Team with those of another CRN Team. These projects address meaningful gaps in the field of PD research that have emerged over the course of the CRN Team's project, including α -synuclein pathology, aggregation kinetics, and disease propagation; cellular quality control and organelle dysfunction; neuroinflammation and genomic regulation; and systemic drivers, bioenergetics, and neuronal vulnerability. This structure is intended to provide Fellows with a broad network of scientific and career mentorship across multiple institutions while fostering a collaborative environment in which the Fellow's independently-led research project can thrive.

Future of the ASAP Collaborative Research Network

The ASAP Collaborative Research Network (CRN) has continued to advance Parkinson's disease (PD) research by emphasizing collaboration and resource generation, as well as data sharing, and has contributed to broadening our understanding of Parkinson's disease.

In the coming year(s), the 19 CRN teams that received supplemental funding will conclude their projects, and 65 new projects across the **PD Heterogeneity** theme, **Tool Generation** theme, Discovery Fellowship, and MoMa will begin. Our collaborative efforts with other organizations, such as the Allen Institute, The 10,000 Brains Project, and Catalyst Neuro, will continue to align research priorities and build infrastructure and resources that bridge gaps and drive progress.

Conclusion

The ASAP CRN has demonstrated that open science policies and collaboration can accelerate discoveries and build a thriving research ecosystem. By providing foundational, field-enabling resources and datasets, fostering collaboration, and establishing infrastructure and standards, the CRN has stimulated breakthroughs in PD research. The CRN will continue to drive progress, ensuring the tools and knowledge needed to treat PD are available to the global PD community.

You can access a full list of preprints and publications associated with ASAP through the **[ASAP BioRxiv Channel](#)** and the **[ASAP PubMed Collection](#)**.

